

Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids. Part XII. " Zonal effect " in the Change of Refractivity during Mutual Coagulations.

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In Part X of this series (Joshi and Panikkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 797; also *J. chim. Phys.*, 1935, **32**, 455) results were given for the change of viscosity during a number of *mutual* coagulations between oppositely charged sols. Subsequent work in Part XI (Joshi and Jaya Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 141) on the variation of μ , the refractive index of a number of coagulating systems showed that this property is sufficiently sensitive and can be employed with convenience in order to follow the course of a coagulation. In the literature of the subject, *mutual* coagulations have been but scantily examined in respect of their kinetics. It was of interest, therefore, to study these by use of this new method, *viz.*, change of refractivity.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The colloidal solutions of manganese dioxide, arsenious sulphide and ferric oxide were prepared and estimated for their colloid contents as described in Part X (*loc. cit.*). The last quantities were respectively 2.1 g. of MnO_2 , 3.0 g. of As_2S_3 and 1.5 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre. The general procedure, precautions as to constancy of temperature etc., and the observation of changes in μ are described in Part XI (*loc. cit.*). In experiments corresponding to curves No. 1 to 4 varying amounts of the As_2S_3 sol were diluted with water to 1 c.c., and mixed in the refractometer cell with an equal volume of the Fe_2O_3 sol at a known time, the two sols having been pre-heated to 35° . Curve 5 relates to the use of colloid MnO_2 instead of colloid As_2S_3 . These results are shown in Table I, and partly by μ -time curves in Fig. 1.

TABLE I.

Amounts of the sols.			Curve No.	Remarks.
1 C.c. Fe_2O_3 + 1 c.c. As_2S_3	+ 0.0 c.c. H_2O		1	No flocculation in first 60 mins.
+ 0.5 "	+ 0.5 "		2	No flocculation.
+ 0.2 "	+ 0.8 "		3	Flocculation after 65 mins.
+ 0.1 "	+ 0.9 "		4	Copious flocculation after 70 mins.
+ 0.25 c.c. MnO_2 + 0.75			5	Complete coagulation in about 60 mins.
+ 1 "	+ 0		Not shown	No flocculation.

DISCUSSION

It is seen from these results that the occurrence of discontinuities is as conspicuous in these *mutual* as in the electrolytic coagulations reported earlier in Part XI (*loc. cit.*). Further support to this conclusion has been obtained recently in these laboratories in the variation of the transparency of coagulating sols. These results will be published shortly. It may, therefore, be generalised that this *zonal effect* is almost a characteristic of the act of coagulation. The problem next to be investigated would, appear therefore, to be the elucidation of factors whose operation suppresses or marks the occurrence of the *zonal effect* in rapid coagulations.

FIG. 1.

In work in this series, as is usually the practice in studies of coagulation kinetics, record of the progress of the change was discontinued as soon as the system became appreciably heterogeneous by the production of flocculi. This is the principal source of the not

too well defined a term, *turbidity*, so familiar in coagulation effects. Now an interesting observation was made that the coagulation-time curves, corresponding (i) to the incipience of flocculation and turbidity (curves No. 3, 4, 5) and (ii) when these effects were unnoticed (curves 1, 2), belonged essentially to the same family of curves, all characterised by a similar and marked *zonal effect*. Precisely similar observations were made in a number of μ -time curves for coagulation in which the proportion of colloid MnO_2 was varied from 0.2 to 1.0 c.c. mixed (after dilution with water in each case to 1.0 c.c. with 1 c.c. of colloid Fe_2O_3). Since these curves did not show any additional features, only one of them (curve 5) is shown in Fig. 1. Analogous results were obtained earlier (Part XI, *loc. cit.*; cf. also Joshi and Panikkar, *Proc. Acad. Sci. U.P.*, *loc. cit.* also, *J. chim. Phys.*, *loc. cit.*) in the finding that marked changes of viscosity occurred independently of whether the corresponding mixture showed flocculation effect such as the familiar rise in turbidity.

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Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids. Part XIII. "Zonal effect" in the Opacity Changes in the Coagulation of Colloid Manganese Dioxide.

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In Parts XI and XII of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 141, 309; cf. also, *Current Science*, 1936, **4**, 481), it was observed that the change of the refractive index of the above sol during any one of its numerous electrolytic and mutual coagulations examined showed an unmistakable and characteristic 'zonal effect,' which became more conspicuous, the *slower* the change. The present paper records observations of this effect, it would appear for the first time in the field of coagulation kinetics, in the change of the *opacity* during coagulation.